

Synthesis of Benzyl Mercaptals

I. D. Shah and J. P. Trivedi

Several mercaptals are known as therapeutic agents¹. Mercaptals having the structure $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{C}(\text{S} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}-p)_2$ is one of the most effective miticides². Several mercaptals have been patented as pesticides. Chloral mercaptals of the formula $\text{Cl}_3\text{C} \cdot \text{CH}(\text{S} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{R}-p)_2$ are used as pesticides, acaricides and fungicides.³

Various mercaptals containing benzyl moiety have been synthesised by the present authors to study the effect of chemical constitution on the pesticidal and bacteriostatic activity since benzyl group enhances the insecticidal and bacteriostatic activity⁴.

TABLE I

*X.	M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.		M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.
A. R = Ph.				B. R = o-Tol.				
H	61°	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ S ₂	18.8	19.0	55°	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ S ₂	18.0	18.3
o-Me	156°/20mm	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ S ₂	17.4	17.6	140°/22mm	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ S ₂	16.8	17.0
m-Me	138°/20	"	17.4	17.6	120°	"	16.8	17.0
p-Me	225°	"	17.2	17.6	65°	"	16.8	17.0
p-Br	140°/25	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ Br ₂ S ₂	12.5	12.0	158°/25	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ Br ₂ S ₂	12.2	12.6
C. R = p-Tol.				D. R = o-HO.C ₆ H ₄ .				
H	60°	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ S ₂	18.0	18.3	87°	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ OS ₂	18.0	18.0
o-Me	115°	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ S ₂	16.9	17.0	162°/30mm	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ OS ₂	16.6	16.8
m-Me	112°	"	10.7	17.0	113°	"	16.4	16.8
p-Me	80°	"	16.9	17.0	211°	"	16.6	16.8
p-Br	147°	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ Br ₂ S ₂	12.4	12.6	115°	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ BrOS ₂	12.2	12.5
p-Cl	..	..	..	..	107°	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ ClOS ₂	15.0	15.2
E. R = piperonyl.				F. R = Cl ₃ C.				
H	118°	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ S ₂	16.4	16.8	83°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ Cl ₃ S ₂	16.6	17.0
o-Me	122°	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₂ S ₂	15.5	15.7	102°	*C ₁₆ H ₁₃ Cl ₃ S ₂	14.0	14.3
m-Me	112°	"	15.3	15.7	147°	†C ₂₀ H ₂₃ Cl ₃ S ₂	14.4	14.7
p-Me	86°	"	15.8	15.7	107°	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ Cl ₃ S ₂	15.6	15.8

N.B. Liquid mercaptals described above could not be distilled at atmospheric pressure since these showed considerable decomposition. All melting points are uncorrected.

*Here X refers to p-Cl.

†Here X ,, 2, 4-Me₂

1. Schirm, Deut., Pat. 715365/1941; *Chem. Abst.*, 1944, 38, 2049; Franz *et al.*, B.P. 501392/1947; *Chem. Abst.*, 1948, 42, 926.

2. Jelinck, U. S.P. 580550/1952; *Chem. Abst.*, 1952, 46, 9600.

3. Schrader, Deut. Pat. 1063152/1959; *Chem. Abst.*, 1961, 55, 13378.

4. Henkel *et al.*, B. P. 807720/1959; *Chem. Abst.*, 1960, 54, 412.

Various benzyl halides were converted into the corresponding benzyl mercaptals by the action of thiourea, as described by Vogel⁵. These benzylmercaptans, when condensed with appropriate aldehydes in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid, afforded the title compounds. The pesticidal properties of these compounds is under investigation.

Method of Preparation of Benzyl Mercaptals

A mixture of an aldehyde (1*M*) and benzylmercaptan (2*M*) was added to a previously ice-cooled (about 0°) sulphuric acid (150 ml) with constant stirring. After the addition was over, the mixture was kept in an ice bath for additional 2 hr. and was finally decomposed in crushed ice when the product was precipitated. It was collected at the pump, washed with ice-water several times till free of acid, and was finally crystallised from benzene or light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°). The average yields range from 45 to 55%. Compounds, thus prepared, are recorded in Table I.

Authors thank the Gujarat State Industrial Research Committee for the award of a research grant to one of the authors (J.P.T.).

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
St. XAVIER'S COLLEGE,
AHMEDABAD-9.

Received January 20, 1964.